

Quality Aspects of Ring Spun Tencel/Polyester and Tencel/Cotton Ply-Twisted Yarns

G. K. Tyagi, Ashvani Goyal* & Pankaj

Department of Textile Technology, the Technological Institute of Textile & Sciences, Bhiwani, India

Abstract:

The paper presents the results of an experimental study on the quality aspects of tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton ply-twisted yarns. Three distinct fibre-mixes of tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton blended ring-spun ply-twisted yarns with varying single and ply - twists were analyzed for their physical properties. It was found that tencel- polyester ply - twisted yarn exhibits superior strength and extensibility compared to tencel-cotton ply-twisted yarn. Achieving higher strength and extensibility necessitates a low singles' yarn twist factor and a high doubling-ratio. Comparable to tencel-cotton ply - twisted yarns, tencel-polyester yarns exhibit greater uniformity; however, the degree of uniformity diminishes as the singles' yarn twist factor increases. The results also showed that tencel- polyester ply -twisted yarn have less hairiness and lower rigidity, the latter increases with an increasing doubling-ratio.

Keywords: *Ring-spun yarn, Tencel blended yarn, Tencel-cotton yarn, Tencel-polyester yarn, Tex twist factor*

*Corresponding Author:

Dr. Ashvani Goyal
Associate Professor & Head,
Department of Textile Technology,
The Technological Institute of Textile & Sciences,
Birla Colony,
Bhiwani – 127 021 Haryana
E-mail: ashvanigoyal@titsbhiwani.ac.in, ashvanigoyal@gmail.com

1. Introduction

With the continuous surge in demand for technical textiles, the need to expand production capacities for plied and folded yarns has escalated significantly. Plied yarns, formed by twisting two or more single yarns, play a crucial role in improving yarn properties and producing higher value products, Ply-twisted yarns exhibit greater regularity, balanced longitudinal variations in individual ends, and compensation for spot defects [1-2]. The twisting process determines the yarn structure, strength, and the handle properties of the resultant product, including bulk, quality, and yarn hairiness.

The development of yarn structural becomes even more complex when the yarn is spun from blends of fiber with dissimilar properties and type [3, 4]. The blending of different fibers is a common practice in the spinning industry to achieve a desirable range of properties that meet end-use requirements and economic considerations. The introduction of new cellulosic fibers like Tencel, along with the availability of fibers with diverse types and properties, has opened a rich variety of materials for blending. Tencel fiber, known for its luxury and practicality, blends seamlessly with other nature and synthetic fibres such as cotton, polyester, lycra or wool, enhancing comfort and performance.

While some researchers have explored the properties of ring-spun tencel, polyester, and cotton single yarns, along with their blends, more information is required for the better practical application of ply -twisted tencel-blended yarns. This paper aims to identify the quality aspects of ply- twisted tencel-polyester and tencel- cotton yarns, focusing on quantifying the physical characteristics of these structures.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Preparation of Yarn Samples

Yarns of 29.5 Tex were spun from tencel and its blend with polyester and cotton fibres using three different blend ratios (25:75, 50:50, 75:25,) and Tex twist factor ranging from 28.71 to 47.85. The fibre specifications of tencel,

polyester and cotton fibres are given in Table 1. For blending tencel and polyester fibres, each of the two components was hand opened and sandwiched well to produce a homogeneous blend. However, for tencel-cotton blended yarns, the combed cotton sliver was blended with tencel fibre in the opening room. The conversion to drawn sliver was carried out by using a MMC carding machine and Lakshmi Rieters' drawframe DO/2S. Two drawing passages were given to the card sliver, the linear density of finisher sliver being adjusted to 3.69 ktex. The finisher sliver, converted into 492 Tex roving on an OKK flyframe, was used to produce 29.5 Tex yarn on Lakshmi Rieters' G5/1 ring frame using a spindle speed of 12,000 rpm. For plying, two single yarns of 29.5 Tex were first parallel wound on a parrel winder for a suitable package and were later S- twisted on Texmaco ring doubler running at 8500 rpm. All plied yarns were twisted at three different doubling ratios (doubling to single twist ratio, D/S ratio) of 0.35, 0.53 and 0.71 for preparing final plied yarns of tencel – polyester and tencel-cotton blends.

Table 1– Specifications of Tencel, Polyester and Cotton fibers

Fibre	Length, mm	Linear density, dtex	Tenacity, cN/tex	Breaking elongation %	Modulus, cN/tex
Tencel	38	1.40	31.3	7.2	731.3
Polyester	38	1.33	56.2	10.8	698.9
Cotton	33.1 ^a	1.18	24.9	6.5	525.5

^a Span length, 2.5%

2.2 Tests

All the yarns were tested for single strand strength and breaking extension on an Instron (Model 4411) using 500 mm test specimen and 200 mm/min cross- head speed. The tensile parameters were averaged from 50 observations for each yarn sample. Yarn irregularity was determined using the Uster Evenness Tester (UT-III). The flexural rigidity was measured on weighted ring yarn stiffness tester by ring loop method [5]. Zweigle hairiness meter (Model G565) was used to record yarn hairiness. The hairiness was tested at speed of 50 m/min for 4 minutes and an average of ten readings is taken.

3. Results and Discussion

The influence of three experimental factors, namely blend ratio, single yarn Tex twist factor, and doubling- ratio (D/S ratio) on the yarn characteristics, was assessed for significance using ANOVA analysis (Table 2). The confidence level used was 99%. The main factors significantly influenced most properties for both tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton blended ply-twisted yarns, except imperfection.

Table 2 - ANOVA results for Tencel-polyester and Tencel-cotton blended ring spun plied yarns

Fibre type	Process variables	Properties										
		Tenacity	Breaking elongation	Unevenness	Imperfection				Flexural rigidity	Hairiness		
					Thin	Thick	Neps	Total		N1	N2	S3
Tencel-Polyester	B	S	S	S	ns	ns	ns	ns	S	S	S	S
	C	S	S	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	S	S	S	S
	D	S	ns	s	ns	ns	ns	ns	S	S	S	S
Tencel-Cotton	B	S	S	S	ns	S	S	S	S	ns	ns	ns
	C	S	S	ns	ns	S	S	S	ns	S	S	S
	D	S	ns	s	ns	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

s- Significant at 99% significance level; ns- Not significant at 99% significance level

B- Tencel %; C-Single yarn tex twist factor; D- Double to single yarn twist ratio

3.1 Tenacity

As expected, the tenacity of both tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton yarns tends to increase after plying (Table 3). During plying, the twist is applied in the opposite direction to that of single yarns, resulting in the parallelization of fibers. Consequently, more fibers share the load during tensile loading, leading to increased yarn tenacity [6-7]. Regardless of single yarn twist, tenacity continues to increase due to ply twist for both tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton yarns. This phenomenon persists across the entire set of yarns under investigation; however, the level of increase in tenacity differs between tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton yarns. In the case of tencel-polyester yarns, the tenacity of ply - twisted yarns majorly decrease with an increase in single yarn twist. Conversely, tencel-cotton ply-twisted yarns spun with higher cotton content display an increase in tenacity with an increase in singles' as well as ply twist. These results reaffirm that doubling-ratio is the most influential parameter determining yarn tenacity. Simultaneously, the composition of the fibre-mix in the blended yarns also affects the tenacity of the ply-

twisted yarns. As seen in Table 3, increasing tencel content in the fibre- mix increases the tenacity of tencel-cotton ply-twisted yarns but adversely affects the tenacity of tencel-polyester yarns. This behavior is quite understandable and arises due to the higher tenacity and breaking extension of tencel fibre than cotton and lower tensile properties than polyester fibre.

3.2 Breaking extension

Table 3 shows the breaking extension values of tencel blended ply - twisted yarns. Generally, tencel-polyester ply-twisted yarns exhibit higher breaking extension than their tencel-cotton counterparts. A positive correlation exists between doubling-ratio and yarn extension, indicating an increase in breaking extension. As observed in Table 3, a higher plied yarn extension can be achieved with a low single yarn twist factor in combination with a high doubling- ratio. Conversely, ply-twisted yarns produced with high single yarn twist display lower breaking extension, which increases with an increasing doubling -ratio. Regarding the fibre mix composition, the breaking extension of ply - twisted yarns follows the same trend as tenacity. In the case of tencel-polyester ply-twisted yarns, the breaking extension increases with an increase in proportion of polyester fibre in the mix. Similarly, the breaking extension of tencel-cotton ply-twisted yarns decreases with an increase in cotton content in the mix. These trends are expected consequences of the significant differences in the breaking extension of polyester and cotton fibres. Additionally, all the ply - twisted yarns show higher breaking extension when plied with a high twist factor. This can be attributed to the fact that a higher twist in the yarn provides better packing and obliquity of fibres, making the yarn more extensible [8].

Table 3 - Influence of single twist factor and doubling ratio on tenacity, breaking extension and flexural rigidity of ring spun tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton blended plied yarns at different blend ratios.

Fiber type	Blend ratio	Single yarn tex twist factor	Tenacity, g/tex			Breaking elongation, %			Flexural Rigidity, dyne-cm ² * 10 ⁻¹					
			Single yarn	Ply-twisted yarn		Single yarn	Ply-twisted yarn		Single yarn	Ply-twisted yarn				
				0.35 ^a	0.53 ^a		0.71 ^a	0.35 ^a		0.53 ^a	0.71 ^a	0.35 ^a	0.53 ^a	0.71 ^a
Tencel: polyester	25:75	28.71	25.95	28.04	30.39	30.41	10.65	10.89	11.06	12.62	3.03	4.14	4.35	4.92
		38.28	25.29	28.96	29.71	31.68	11.16	11.49	11.69	11.88	3.33	4.59	4.95	5.17
		47.85	24.12	25.15	26.36	26.79	12.48	9.02	8.84	9.46	3.71	5.17	5.51	5.71
	50:50	28.71	24.54	26.72	27.01	28.16	9.09	9.66	9.9	8.96	3.09	4.68	4.92	5.44
		38.28	22.95	25.22	26.58	27.06	9.61	10.59	10.24	10.42	3.71	5.17	5.62	5.84
		47.85	20.28	22.53	22.81	22.91	9.82	8.91	8.75	9.18	4.84	5.44	5.64	6.87
	75:25	28.71	23.27	23.73	25.05	26.48	7.96	8.05	8.12	8.17	4.55	5.17	5.44	5.92
		38.28	22.7	23.77	24.83	25.48	8.19	9.01	9.2	9.75	4.67	5.87	6.29	6.73
		47.85	20.02	21.63	21.77	21.9	8.69	8.87	8.44	9.04	5.66	6.28	6.73	7.04
Tencel: cotton	25:75	28.71	17.49	16.97	18.45	20.45	5.62	6.48	7.04	7.19	2.94	3.94	4.92	4.92
		38.28	19.52	16.57	18.11	20.13	6.66	6.69	6.72	6.8	3.88	4.35	4.68	5.17
		47.85	18.03	16.62	16.89	18.89	7.06	5.38	5.67	6.03	2.89	4.17	4.35	4.97
	50:50	28.71	18.59	19.54	19.79	20.95	5.89	6.73	7.13	7.37	4.22	5.35	5.44	5.9
		38.28	20.54	22.47	22.85	23.15	6.21	6.64	6.75	6.85	4.57	5.25	5.77	5.85
		47.85	19.31	20.17	20.26	20.44	6.36	6.43	6.08	6.53	3.72	5.26	5.35	5.44
	75:25	28.71	20.83	21.38	21.7	23.73	5.93	7.59	8.29	9.13	4.73	5.92	5.92	6.16
		38.28	20.15	21.06	21.21	21.79	6.51	6.72	6.85	6.89	5.44	5.94	6.04	7.11
		47.85	18.37	19.51	20.18	20.75	6.75	6.87	6.19	7.11	4.83	6.3	7.68	7.87

^a Double to single yarn twist ratio

3.3 Flexural rigidity

Table 3 shows the flexural rigidity values of different yarns. The presence of tencel fibre in the fibre mix increases the flexural rigidity of both types of blended yarns. This can be attributed to the higher modulus and lower bulk of tencel fibre compared to polyester and cotton fibre, which aids in increasing the packing of fibres and impedes the freedom of fibre movement [9]. Furthermore, the flexural rigidity values of both tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton ply-twisted yarns are significantly higher than the corresponding single yarns and further increase with an increasing doubling-ratio. This is due to the wrapping of single twisted yarns around each other in a plied yarn, which always reduces the freedom of fibre movement as compared to that in single yarn structure, resulting in higher flexural rigidity of the ply- twisted yarns [10].

3.4 Unevenness and Imperfections

The unevenness of singles and ply – twisted yarns depend on various factors. The single yarn twist plays an important role, but other factors such as the composition of the fibre-mix and doubling-ratio also have significant influence. As can be seen from Table 4, unevenness of all the single yarns increases with an increasing single twist factor. The reason for the increased unevenness is the higher crimp added to the yarn, which gives a wavy effect to the structure due to mechanical hinderance [11].

For all yarns, the unevenness reduces significantly after plying. However, the unevenness of ply-twisted yarns slightly increases with an increase in single yarn twist factor, most likely due to obstruction in fibre movement at the nip of the front roller [12]. Interestingly, tencel- cotton ply-twisted yarns exhibit more reduction in unevenness than those of tencel-polyester yarns, irrespective of single yarn twist. Furthermore, the unevenness of all ply – twisted yarns increases with an increase in doubling- ratio; tencel- cotton ply-twisted yarns display more unevenness compared to their tencel-polyester counterparts.

Imperfection figures of tencel- cotton and tencel-polyester single and ply-twisted yarns, as shown in Table 4, reduce considerably on plying. Tencel- cotton ply-twisted yarns show more thick places, thin places and neps compared to tencel-polyester ply-twisted yarns. However, there is no specific trend for reduction in imperfections with San increase in doubling-ratio.

Table 4 - Influence of single twist factor and doubling ratio on unevenness and imperfections/km of ring spun tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton blended plied yarns at different blend ratios.

Fiber type	Blend ratio	Single yarn tex twist factor	Unevenness, U%				Imperfections/km			
			Single yarn	Ply-twisted yarn			Single yarn	Ply-twisted yarn		
				0.35 ^a	0.53 ^a	0.35 ^a		0.35 ^a	0.53 ^a	0.35 ^a
Tencel: polyester	25:75	28.71	8.95	6.39	6.42	7.33	2	0	4	0
		38.28	9.26	6.12	6.37	6.38	0	0	0	0
		47.85	9.46	6.44	6.49	6.75	0	0	0	0
	50:50	28.71	9.27	6.31	6.61	6.72	0	0	0	0
		38.28	9.54	6.27	6.33	6.43	2	0	4	4
		47.85	9.64	6.59	6.70	7.07	3	0	0	0
	75:25	28.71	9.59	6.76	7.10	7.16	1	0	0	0
		38.28	10.22	6.53	6.99	7.39	2	2	4	0
		47.85	10.51	6.20	6.80	7.05	6	2	0	0
Tencel: cotton	25:75	28.71	12.29	8.07	8.53	9.44	16	0	4	0
		38.28	11.81	8.32	8.53	8.69	24	0	0	4
		47.85	13.2	8.61	8.63	9.14	16	0	10	0
	50:50	28.71	11.59	7.89	8.05	8.53	18	4	2	0
		38.28	11.7	7.83	7.88	8.86	13	0	0	4
		47.85	12.36	7.70	7.87	8.23	12	6	0	0
	75:25	28.71	11.35	7.51	7.66	8.23	28	0	0	0
		38.28	11.56	8.21	8.76	9.28	12	4	1	0
		47.85	11.68	7.72	7.95	8.95	9	3	0	0

^a Double to single yarn twist ratio

3.5 Hairiness

Table 5 shows the yarn hairiness value in class N1 (<1mm long), N2 (<2mm long) and S3 (>3mm long) for ring-spun tencel blended single and ply-twisted yarns. As expected, the hairiness of both types of yarns is greatly affected by the change in single yarn twist factor. An increase in the single yarn twist factor leads to a decrease in both short and long hairs irrespective of the composition of the fibre mix. However, the effect of single yarn twist factor on hairiness is more pronounced in tencel- cotton yarns. This reduction in hairiness occurs because high twist enables the fibres to traverse towards the yarn axis owing to a high rate of migration, resulting in firm embedment of fibres in the main body of the yarns [13]. Table 5 also shows that both tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton ply-twisted yarns display a drastic decline in hairiness compared to their singles counterparts, and the

number of hairs in all three length classes decreases with an increase in doubling-ratio. At a high doubling- ratio, the high compression force on the strands and the low twist in the strands make the strands flatten at the point of contact between the strands. Hence, an increase in ply twist reduces hairiness [14]. An increase in ply twist also decreases the number of hairs in all three length classes in statistically meaningful terms. This is because ply twist causes the hairs of single strands to be trapped between the strands or wrapped on the surface of the yarn, resulting in a decrease in hairiness.

4. Conclusión

- a. The properties of ply-twisted yarns depend solely on the doubling ratio and the composition of fibre-mix. Generally, tencel-polyester ply-twisted yarns are stronger, more extensible, more even, and have fewer imperfections compared to their tencel-cotton counterparts. Increasing the doubling ratio enhances the tenacity, breaking extension, and evenness of ply-twisted yarns, regardless of the composition of the fibre mix.
- b. The doubling ratio is also a crucial factor for the hairiness and flexural rigidity of ply-twisted yarns. Increasing the doubling ratio reduces hairiness in both types of yarns but adversely affects flexural rigidity. Under all experimental conditions, tencel-polyester yarns exhibit less hairiness and more flexural rigidity, even after plying.

Table 5 - Influence of single twist factor and doubling ratio on hairiness of ring spun tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton blended plied yarns at different blend ratios

Fiber type	Blend ratio	Single yarn tex twist factor	Hairiness/10m											
			Single yarn			Ply-twisted yarn								
						0.35 ^a			0.53 ^a			0.71 ^a		
			N1	N2	S3	N1	N2	S3	N1	N2	S3	N1	N2	S3
Tencel: polyester	25:75	28.71	1015	117	12	2483	286	51	1940	219	43	1748	186	23
		38.28	905	83	12	1731	175	25	1413	133	12	1358	118	10
		47.85	870	79	11	1357	132	10	1175	39	8	1146	16	7
	50:50	28.71	853	72	20	2368	267	48	2221	215	39	1659	155	24
		38.28	801	56	15	1754	157	30	1449	121	19	1335	112	18
		47.85	54	7	8	1328	19	7	1155	16	6	754	10	5
	75:25	28.71	755	51	31	2587	293	56	2369	237	46	1654	152	32
		38.28	702	44	27	1536	123	37	1268	91	23	1204	85	21
		47.85	654	40	25	963	72	23	911	60	12	831	53	6
Tencel: cotton	25:75	28.71	1402	161	33	3086	398	77	2989	364	52	1974	210	29
		38.28	1019	106	23	1922	186	39	1659	152	35	1580	127	22
		47.85	996	99	20	1427	141	25	1394	141	23	1179	22	19
	50:50	28.71	1240	123	29	3430	429	96	3170	374	73	1926	193	40
		38.28	1017	84	25	2008	172	31	1559	137	26	1513	132	22
		47.85	933	85	22	1371	163	16	979	87	15	673	59	13
	75:25	28.71	1309	117	39	3456	371	83	2985	282	82	1921	173	39
		38.28	1112	96	37	2246	201	41	2117	189	31	1599	136	27
		47.85	1101	80	34	1664	134	25	1403	129	24	1337	113	15

^a Double to single yarn twist ratio

References:

- [1] Tyagi G K, Quality aspects of two-for-one and ring-twisted OE rotor-spun plied yarns, *Indian J. Fibre Text. Res.*, Vol.31, June 2006, pp.293-297
- [2] O Ozdemir, S Sardag & F Kalaoglu, Effect of twisting methods on plied yarn properties, *Indian J. Fibre Text. Res.*, Vol.31, Sept 2006, pp. 394-400
- [3] Kaushik RCD, Salhotra KR & Tyagi G K, influence of doubling on characteristics of acrylic-viscose rayon rotor-spun yarns, *Indian J. Fibre Text. Res.*, Vol.-12, sept.1987, pp.142-145
- [4] Tyagi G K & Chatterjee KN, Contribution of doubling to the characteristics of polyester/cotton ring and rotor spun yarns, *Indian J. Fibre Text. Res.*, Vol.-17, Mar 1992, pp. 9-14

- [5] Owen J D and Riding G, The weighted ring stiffness test, *J Text Inst*, 55(1964) T414
- [6] Tyagi G k, R. Chattopadhyay, Physical characteristic of tencel-polyester and tencel-cotton yarns produced on ring, rotor and air-jet spinning machines. *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, vol.-38, sept. 2013, pp, 230-236
- [7] Basu Arindam and Gotipamul L Rajanna, Quality characteristics of polyester/viscose and polyester/cotton two ply yarns, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 31(2006), 279-285
- [8] Louis A. Fiori, John J. Brown, and Jack E. Sands, Effect of single and ply twists on the properties of a 31/2 carded cotton yarn. *Text Res J*, March 1954, pp 267-272
- [9] Wooding C, Regenerated Cellulosic Fibres, Woodhead publishing Limited, Cambridge, 2001, Vol.12, No.6, 290-304
- [10] Chattopadhyay R, Strategic responses by Hong Kong textile and clothing firms towards MFA, *J Text Inst*, 88(1997) 76-78
- [11] Tyagi G K, Ajay R, Gupta S & Kapoor V, Influence of fiber linear density, twist and direct dye on physical and dye-uptake characteristics of viscose rayon yarns, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 11 (1986) 150
- [12] Tyagi G K, Bhowmick M, Bhattacharyya S and Kumar R, Effect of spinning conditions on mechanical and performance characteristics of cotton ring and compact spun yarns, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 35(2010) 21-30
- [13] Tyagi G K, Sharma K R, Goyal A & Singh M, Variation in polyester-viscose and polyester-cotton ring and rotor yarn characteristics as a consequence of fibre cross-section, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 29 (2004) 184
- [14] Palaniswamy k, Mohamed Peer A, Effect of the single yarn twist and ply to single yarn twist ratio on the hairiness and abrasion resistance of cotton two-ply yarn, *Autex research journal*, Vol.6, No.2, June 2006